

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE RESEARCH SOFTWARE GUIDELINE

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INTRODUCTION

This guideline is an addition to the [University of Twente \(UT\) Research Software Policy](#) and goes into more detail on the prescribed workflow for the research software output of the UT staff. It also provides additional background and considerations for registering, documenting, licensing, commercializing and managing research software.

GUIDELINE OBJECTIVES

This guideline aims to help the UT staff adhere to the research software policy and management standards when developing research software and to ensure the long-term sustainability of their software.

Since the standards and needs of the researchers change over time, this guideline is intended to be a living document, allowing for further improvements, updates and amendments based on future input and developments.

From version 1.3 onwards, this document has been open to comments and feedback of UT staff at the [internal SharePoint space](#). Major updates to the Guideline and Policy will be shared with the public at [UT's Zenodo community page](#). An abridged online version of this guideline is available on the [UT Service Portal > Research Software Management](#).

SOFTWARE MANAGEMENT PLAN

It is important that software is developed with sustainability in mind. For this reason, the research software must be well documented and preferably published under an open-source license to ensure the ability to reproduce results and assess findings' reliability. This is also in line with the [strategic goals](#) of the Open Science NL national program to make research software FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

The [UT Research Software Policy](#) and this Guideline therefore set certain responsibilities for the research software management.

Naturally, some research software would require more care than others, depending on the length or complexity of the source code, the scope of its purpose, its type, and its potential uses –including valorisation for commercial purposes. The [Practical Guide to Software Management Plans](#), prepared by the Netherlands eScience Centre, sets three levels of software management (low, medium, and high) depending on the purpose, reliability, and maintenance. We will follow their categorization in this guideline.

Those developing and managing software are responsible for:

- 1) Writing a software management plan (SMP), if the software management level is medium or high
- 2) Providing appropriate embedded and supporting documentation (e.g. user documentation, deployment documentation, and if applicable, developer documentation) for their software
- 3) Making use of a version-controlled environment for managing software (e.g. UT's GitLab, Codeberg, BitBucket or GitHub)
- 4) Respecting the license conditions when reusing software created by others, as well as attributing them by citing reused software

- 5) Publishing software as open source where possible and appropriate, following the procedure outlined in this guideline.

Those supervising software developers are responsible for:

- Ensuring that team members have, where required, training in developing and managing software
- Ensuring that when publishing open-source software, the UT requirements regarding software registration on Pure are followed
- Ensuring that when publishing open-source software, the UT Research Software Decision Tree below is adhered to.

APPLICABLE PROCEDURES

Please follow the UT Research Software Management Decision Tree below to determine if an open-source software license can be applied for your project. If your project goes through these steps successfully, make sure to follow the Open-Source Checklist to meet all the requirements before publishing.

Some of the widely used open-source licenses are pre-approved by the UT, listed and explained in the Appendix. Regardless of the license chosen, a description of your software and other metadata must be registered on Pure.

If in doubt, please consult the UT Software Stewards for any of these steps by emailing softwarestewards@utwente.nl

UT RESEARCH SOFTWARE MANAGEMENT DECISION TREE

FIGURE 1: UT RESEARCH SOFTWARE MANAGEMENT DECISION TREE

A DETAILED WALKTHROUGH OF DECISION TREE:

1. Do you have full ownership of the research software?

- No:
 - Review contracts or agreements for Third Parties' rights
Contact UT's lawyers at research-lawyer-ga@utwente.nl for questions
- Yes: Go to the next step

2. If you link to, include or use lines of code from others, are you allowed to use other code in a compatible manner?

- No:
 - Check the Open-Source Software Licenses Compatibility Table
Contact Software Stewards softwarestewards@utwente.nl for questions
- Yes: Go to the next step

3. Are the legal or ethical restrictions regarding the publication of your research software cleared?

- No:
 - Check Export Control Restrictions
Contact Knowledge Safety Team at knowledge-safety@utwente.nl
 - Check personal data and GDPR restrictions
Contact [Privacy Contact Person](#) at your faculty
 - For AI systems contact Software Stewards softwarestewards@utwente.nl for questions
 - For ethics concerns, ask for a review by contacting the [Ethics Committee](#) of your faculty
- Yes: Go to the next step

4. Do you want to share your software output publicly and for free, without commercializing?

- No:
 - Contact the [Knowledge & Technology Transfer Office \(KTO\)](#)
Prepare an [Invention Disclosure Form](#) (Annex I)
- Yes: Go to the next step

5. Go to the Open-Source Checklist

STEP 1 – OWNERSHIP

The "ownership" step is essential to determine if the University of Twente has the full (ownership) rights to the software and therefore also the right to publish the software under one of the pre-approved open-source licenses, without any legal or IPR conflicts. This step is aimed at confirming that no third party—such as students, contractors, vendors, consultants, non-employees or external research partners (e.g. industrial partners co-funding the research in which the code was written) (hereinafter: “Third Part(y)(ies)”)—has any existing claim to the software, co-owns the software or even owns the software outright.

If your project involves any such third parties, including UT students (e.g. working as teaching assistants in your research group, or contribute and collaborate to your code in the context of a broader funded research project) you would need to clarify ownership via a Contributor License Agreement (CLA) or a copyright transfer agreement (see: [IPR Agreements at UT](#)).

Another aspect of ownership is the growing use of AI assistants in code development. Software code written by a generative AI tool should be handled with care. First and foremost, one cannot assume the code is correct and/or secure at the current level of publicly available AI tools. Therefore, make sure to test extensively the code snippets developed this way. A growing concern in this field is that while the machine generated code is [not copyrightable in the U.S. law](#), most generative AI tools are not transparent about their training data. These tools may come up with code parts equal to existing copyrighted code. You must check whether that is the case.

Why: Understanding who contributed either intellectually and/or financially to the code or to the research in which the code was written helps establish who might have legal claims to it (or even owns the software outright). If the University is not the full owner of the software concerned, or if the software concerned is encumbered by (access) rights of a Third Party (e.g. due to a specific Third Party (co-)financing the research in which the code was written), we might not even be able to decide independently to make the software concerned available under one of the pre-approved open source licenses.

Actions: Review any contracts or agreements that relate to the development of the software. Furthermore, establish whether any Third Parties contributed either intellectually and/or financially to the development of the software (e.g. students writing a part of the code or a contractor paying the full costs of the research in which the code was written). A general rule of thumb here is looking for explicit IPR arrangements in relevant contracts or agreements. For example, in subsidized projects we typically grant certain access rights to the research results, including the software developed, if a Third Party contributes in-cash and/or in-kind to the project.

In case of any concerns and/or questions relating to this particular step, please contact our lawyers via research-lawyer-ga@utwente.nl. The lawyers of UT can advise on these matters and decide on further steps.

STEP 2 – ASSESS DEPENDENCIES AND OPEN-SOURCE COMPONENTS

It is good practice to keep track of the origin of all code included in the software. This is not only necessary for proper documentation, but also to know what type of license can (or even should) be used when reusing code from others and to correctly attribute it.

Why: All software should have a license distributed with it. Proprietary software cannot be used without explicit written permission from the owner. This is clarified in the end-user license agreement that is prompted during installation or first use, and it is oftentimes highly restrictive. For

open-source software, the pre-existing applicable license might automatically provide, for example, permission to reuse, remix, make derivatives based on that code, and redistribute without any further permission from the owners. However, the same pre-existing applicable license might also result in the obligation to publish (e.g.) any ‘derivative works under the same open-source license.

Actions: Assess whether your software has certain dependencies and/or (builds upon) open-source components. The following questions here might be relevant: Did you link to, include or use lines of code from others? Are you allowed to use other code in a compatible manner? Can you even choose the license yourself or are you bound by another pre-existing applicable open-source license?

The table below depicts the compatibility of some of the most common open-source software licenses. Note that the compatibility is unidirectional in some cases; therefore, the license of the earlier software on the most left column determines whether it is possible to combine it with the other license options in the following columns.

TABLE 1: OPEN-SOURCE SOFTWARE LICENSES COMPATIBILITY

Combine with? →	CC0	MIT	BSD	Apache	EUPL	GPL, AGPL or LGPL	Proprietary
CC0	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
MIT	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
BSD	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Apache 2.0	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	Claused
EUPL	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
GPL, AGPL or LGPL	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
Proprietary	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Depends on license

Next steps: note that the questions stipulated above are mere examples and thus not limitative. If you have used lines of code from other software, are building upon or using existing (open-source or proprietary) software or are unsure about any of these things please contact UT’s Software Stewards at softwarestewards@utwente.nl

STEP 3 – LEGAL OR ETHICAL RESTRICTIONS

The “legal or ethical restrictions” step aims to ensure that releasing software under one of the pre-approved open-source licenses complies with specific regulatory frameworks that may limit or impose specific conditions on how the software is distributed or made available publicly. This step focuses on four key legal and ethical areas.

A. EXPORT CONTROL RESTRICTIONS

Why: Export control laws in (e.g.) the EU and US regulate the export (i.e. publishing of) software that may e.g. contain encryption or other sensitive technologies. Releasing such software publicly could violate these laws if the software concerned is distributed under an open-source license.

Action: Determine if the software contains sensitive technologies and/or might be used for military purposes. Common examples would be encryption technology, sensitive algorithms or restricted data handling protocols. The full list of relevant technologies (within the EU) is laid down in the [EU Dual-Use Regulation](#) and [EU Common Military List](#). A general rule of thumb is to search (via a control F search) for relevant keywords such as, for example, “cryptographic”. It is also good practice (as written down in step 2) to “keep track of the origin of all code included in the software” since including code of others might result in violations of foreign export control laws. For example, the U.S. Department of Commerce Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS) and the International Traffic in Arms Regulations (ITAR) control certain technologies and might also require a license for re-exporting (i.e. publishing) the software concerned.

Next Steps: If the software is subject to these controls, you may need to apply for an export license or restrict the software’s distribution to ensure compliance. In case of any doubt please contact Knowledge Safety Team at knowledge-safety@utwente.nl

B. RESTRICTIONS FROM THE EU ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT (“AI ACT”)

Why: The AI Act imposes restrictions on the use and distribution of AI systems, especially those that fall under “high-risk” categories. Releasing certain types of AI systems as open source could require compliance with specific obligations that flow down from the AI Act.

Action: Identify whether the software includes any AI components. If it does, evaluate if it falls under the AI Act’s definitions of “high-risk” applications (e.g. biometric identification, critical infrastructure, employment-related AI). High-risk AI systems must meet specific transparency, safety, and accountability requirements before release.

Next Steps: If the software is considered high-risk or contains AI components in general, you should (first) consider additional compliance steps such as impact assessments, transparency documentation, or modifying features to align with AI Act requirements. An online tool built for this purpose is available at: artificialintelligenceact.eu

C. EU GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION COMPLIANCE (“GDPR”)

Why: The GDPR governs how personal data is collected, stored, and processed in the EU. Open-sourcing software that handles personal data without privacy safeguards can expose the organization to GDPR violations, especially if the software could be used to process identifiable personal data.

Action: Confirm that the software does not include personal data handling as part of its core functionality. If it does, ensure that personal data is anonymized or removed from the codebase before release. Additionally, include guidelines to inform users of their GDPR obligations if they adapt the software for processing personal data.

Next Steps: if the software includes personal data (handling) as part of its core functionality and if it is not possible to anonymize, please contact [Privacy Contact Person](#) at your faculty.

D. ETHICS

Why: Besides legal restrictions, there might also be ethical reasons not to make your software available. For example, if your software was used for vulnerability discovery in cyber security research. In this case, only publish your code after the vulnerabilities are patched. Another example is AI code or models that were mainly used for testing the model, but where the training data could be biased. In that case the code must not be published.

Note that software used in the execution of clinical investigations with human subjects will practically always require verification and risk analysis, following requirements from the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) or Medical Research involving Human Subjects Act (WMO). This will result in your software management level being high and come with additional requirements.

Action: Make sure there are no ethics issues with publishing your software or make sure that all the requirements in your research domain are met.

Next steps: Ask for an ethics review before you start your research by contacting the [Ethics Committee](#) of your research domain.

STEP 4 – COMMERCIAL EXPLOITATION:

Regardless of the outcome of the steps described above, there might be a desire to refrain from making the software concerned available under one of pre-approved open-source licenses, if UT or your research collaborators see commercial opportunities.

Why: Establishing whether the software concerned might be commercially exploitable is important due to UT having the formal task of valorising its research output. For example, the software might be commercially exploitable either directly or through offering consultancy services. Additionally, the software might even present a novel technical solution to a problem.

Action: Establish whether you or UT want to commercialize your software output, that you have full ownership of.

Next steps: Contact the [Knowledge & Technology Transfer Office](#) (KTO) and prepare an [Invention Disclosure Form](#) (See Annex I of the Implementing Rules on Intellectual Property).

OPEN-SOURCE CHECKLIST (STEP BY STEP)

The steps below are advised when you want to publish your research software as open source. Some steps may require learning new skills or taking team-based decisions in the early phase of a research project. The level of detail of some steps depends on the context and goal of the research project.

1. Create a software management plan
2. Choose an open-source licence
3. Organize your code project in a repository (e.g. GitLab, Codeberg, GitHub)
4. Use version control
5. Write clean code and documentation
6. Ensure reproducibility and usability in your development
7. Archive and obtain a DOI for your research software (via Zenodo)
8. Cite the code in your research article, and add a Citation.cff file to your repository
9. Register your research software to your UT institutional profile (Pure)
10. Promote and maintain your code

All data, software, and related materials underlying your research should be preserved for at least 10 years after the conclusion of the research.

1. CREATE A SOFTWARE MANAGEMENT PLAN

The [Practical Guide to Software Management Plans](#), developed by the Netherlands eScience Centre, is a great start. Using the [template](#) provided there, you can anticipate requirements, estimate times, and consider additional activities such as curating and maintaining your code to ensure reusability and reproducibility. A software management plan is valuable when a reviewer or collaborator needs to get an overview of the research software, as well as for documentation purposes.

These are among the tasks you would need to consider for any research software project:

- Define the purpose and scope of the software
- Identify users, contributors, and maintainer responsibilities
- Choose an open-source license (e.g., MIT, Apache 2.0)
- Set policies for versioning, documentation, and quality control
- Plan for archiving, usability, reproducibility, and long-term preservation
- Align with [FAIR4RS principles](#): Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

2. CHOOSE AN OPEN-SOURCE LICENSE

UT has pre-approved open-source software licenses that its staff can choose from when sharing software openly, listed in the Appendix. Please note that it is a living list, based on the demands and uses by the UT staff. This list will be modified and appended when necessary.

If you have no restrictions and no personal preference for a license, you can educate yourself with differences between them and make an informed decision. A major distinction is between the so-called permissive and restrictive (“Copyleft”) open-source licenses.

TABLE 2: COPYLEFT, PERMISSIVE AND PROPRIETARY SOFTWARE LICENSES

Free and Open Source			Proprietary
Copyleft		Permissive	
Strong	Weak		
GPL AGPL	LGPL MPL	BSD MIT Apache	Research only, No copying, No modification

Adapted from: [Netherlands eScience Centre / Software Licensing](#) (CC-BY-SA)

PERMISSIVE SOFTWARE LICENSES (MIT, BSD, APACHE LICENSE 2.0)

These licenses allow end-users to do anything they want with the code, including using it for commercial purposes, if they properly attribute to the original creator.

The **MIT** License is a permissive free software license originating at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in the late 1980s. As a permissive license, it puts only limited restriction on reuse and has, therefore, reasonable license compatibility. The MIT license permits reuse within proprietary software if all copies include a copy of the MIT License terms and the copyright notice. The MIT license ensures that the original authors must be credited. Furthermore, the MIT license ensures that the software is provided “as is”, without any warranties or guarantees. As a result, the researcher cannot be liable for any damage or claim regarding your software.

The **BSD** license is a simple license that merely requires that all code retain the BSD license notice if redistributed in source code format or reproduce the notice if redistributed in binary format. Like the MIT license, the BSD license does not require that source code be distributed at all. The BSD license is also similar to the MIT license in that attribution is secured and disclaimers of warranty are maintained. There are three types of BSD licenses (0, 2 and 3 –clause). UT endorses the use of the 3-Clause BSD License. The 3-Clause BSD License is more detailed than the MIT license and contains a clause restricting use of the names of contributors for endorsement of a derived code without specific permission.

The **Apache License 2.0** is sterner in protecting access rights. This license agreement also contains a “retaliation” clause, which does not allow filing of patent infringement proceedings against people using the Apache 2.0 covered code. It means that if someone files infringement proceedings in court on a software, which was itself a derivative of code under an Apache License 2.0, then they infringe the license itself. As a result, they automatically lose the license and the right to use the software (and therefore their infringement claim is void, and they become the perpetrator). The Apache License 2.0 is still considered a “permissive” license because it can co-exist with other licenses. For example, a basic package can be made freely available under Apache License 2.0, whilst the add-ons and special features are made available (e.g. for a fee) under a proprietary license.

In dealing with start-ups and corporately funded research, UT’s Knowledge and Technology Transfer Office (KTO) observe that the Apache 2.0 license works well for all the different interests at play between university and corporations. It tends not to raise concern from companies investing in R&D projects at the universities, meanwhile protecting the “open” character of the software.

The main drawback associated with MIT, BSD and Apache License 2.0 is that they do not enforce openness on derivative programs.

RESTRICTIVE SOFTWARE LICENSES (GPL, AGPL, LGPL, EUPL)

Another staple in academia is the GPL license, because any software that uses code published under a GPL license must be covered by a GPL license too. GPL is also one of the oldest open-source licenses and has a large and active community of users behind it.

The main drawback associated with GPL is that it is often contractually prohibited in public-private partnerships.

The **GPL** (from the GNU General Public License suite), its derivative LGPL (L from ‘Lesser’), another derivative AGPL (A from Affero) and the EUPL (European Union Public License) are all so-called ‘copyleft’ licenses and thereby more restrictive than the permissive open-source licenses. A copyleft license grants the right to freely distribute copies and modified versions of software with the stipulation that the same rights are preserved in any derivative work.

Of all GPL licenses, **AGPL** (Affero GPL) is the strictest of the group. It was designed specifically with server-based software in mind. It has a clause ensuring that if you run a modified program on a server and let other users communicate with it there, then your server must also allow them to download the source code corresponding to the modified version running there.

LGPL is designed for library routines and is deemed a lighter version of GPL. When another person modifies software released under an LGPL license, it acts like GPL in that it automatically covers the new software too. However, when someone writes software that merely links and uses the library covered by the LGPL license it does not automatically extend itself (whereas GPL does). This can

broaden the potential uses of a library and makes it more accessible to the public at large (especially for those operating under proprietary, Apache, BSD or MIT covered works).

Among these, the **EUPL** license is slightly more permissive because it can co-exist with other permissive open-source software licenses, including MIT, BSD and Apache 2.0, due to the existence of an 'exclusion and compatibility list' in the license. EUPL also aims to be interoperable. See: [Matrix of EUPL compatible open-source licences](#).

For this reason, many companies sponsoring research at technical universities like UT often enact specific clauses in the collaboration agreements prohibiting the use of these copyleft licenses for software to avoid the risk of having their in-house proprietary software "contaminated" with GPL, which would then result in them having to release their proprietary source code to the public.

COMMUNITY AND COHERENCE

Other general recommendations include following the community and choosing coherence.

When you are working in a community it is best to use the license that is associated with that community (e.g. GNU recommends GNU GPLv3 for most programs whereas Cloud Native Computing Foundation prefers to use the Apache License 2.0 by default).

And when feasible, it is also best to maintain license coherence. If you used lines of codes from other software that were all derived from MIT-licensed material, it is preferable to release your resulting software under an MIT-license too.

The UT staff are encouraged to read the description of the licenses and the full license text in the Appendix to understand the implications of their choice.

You can refer to choosealicense.com for more information and guidance on other licenses.

3. ORGANIZE YOUR CODE PROJECT REPOSITORY

To have an organized project repository for your open-source code, you can use the [Meta template for Research software](#). While each project may require a specific organization for a repository, it is advised to follow generic repository templates. You can explore some examples at the [Research Software Directory](#) following good practices, such as:

- Use a software template
- Organize the folder structure clearly
- Use a structured format: /data, /src, /results, /docs,
- Include license, README.md
- Include requirements.txt or environment.yml.

4. USE VERSION CONTROL (GIT)

We advise using Git as a version control system for your code and following the [version control](#) chapter in the Turing Way.

Using Git has many benefits as making developing code and the publishing process easier once you learn the basic usage, such as:

- Initialize Git for a local repository
- Track changes among development branches of your code
- Use .gitignore
- Push to an online repository for archive and sharing

Online repositories such as GitLab, Codeberg, BitBucket or GitHub provide version control by default, and offer further services. [UT has its own GitLab installation](#) in campus that serves as a secure and local solution. [Codeberg](#) is a non-profit organization within EU with ever-growing community dedicated to open source. [GitHub](#) is owned by Microsoft and while it's cloud services and it's AI assistant CoPilot is highly popular, it comes with concerns regarding digital sovereignty of the EU and the company's questionable practices under U.S. jurisdiction against individual rights and freedoms protected in the EU. [BitBucket](#) is another U.S. service owned by a global software services company, Atlassian, which has business interests in large scale organisations. As a researcher working at a public funded institution, you need to be aware of the risks associated with conflicting private and political interests.

5. WRITE CLEAN CODE AND DOCUMENTATION

One key purpose of publishing your code as open source is to make it understandable, reproducible, and reusable by others, which requires documentation and developing code that follows good practices. We advise following the best practices for [Code Documentation](#) and [Code Quality](#) in [The Turing Way](#) book. These practices include:

- Writing modular and documented code
- Providing metadata of the elements in your source-code and repository
- Providing setup scripts and dependency files
- Using Docker or Binder if possible.

Research output documentation usually includes, but not limited to, details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, vocabularies, units of measurement, any assumptions made, and the format and file type of the data. For research software, you should also include dependencies, compiler versions, and a user manual.

Recording the changes you made while preparing your research output is a core part of doing reproducible research. In a collaborative environment, it also helps you keep track of changes made by members of your research group and others in the scientific community. All this makes your work more reproducible, as part of the FAIR research principles.

Preparing clear documentation and version control also has the added advantage of easy access to the current version of your project and ways to look for, retrieve or recover the changes made in the past.

README.MD

As a key component of your research software documentation, a well-structured README file is essential when publishing your code in a public repository. A README file is typically

the first thing other researchers, collaborators, or reviewers will see; it serves as an entry point for understanding, using, and reusing your code.

A strong README enhances Findability and Accessibility and lays out the groundwork for Reusability and Interoperability. It supports others in exploring your software, replicating your results (especially when linked to publications), and potentially building upon your work.

The README file should clearly introduce your project and provide enough context and practical guidance to facilitate adoption by other users. Below is a list of recommended sections your README may include (adapted from [Wikipedia's README article](#)). You can explore the following [README_Template.md](#) as a starting point.

Recommended README Content:

- **Project Title**
A clear and concise name that reflects the purpose of your software.
- **General Information**
Include the author(s), institutional affiliation, a short abstract of the software, and the research motivation.
- **Repository Structure**
Describe the folder and file structure. Explain the purpose of key directories and files.
- **Installation Instructions**
Step-by-step guide on how to install dependencies and set up the environment.
- **Quick Start Example**
Provide a simple, copy-pasteable code to run a basic example of your software.
- **Usage Reference**
Include a summary of the software's main features and usage instructions. If detailed documentation is provided elsewhere, refer to it.
- **Citation Information**
Provide a citation format and the DOI (e.g., from Zenodo) so others can properly reference your software in publications.
- **Related Tools or Resources**
Mention other software tools your code interacts with, extends, or was inspired by.
- **Developer Contact Information**
Include contact details for the main developer(s) or maintainer(s), ideally a professional or institutional email address.
- **License**
State the license under which the software is distributed (e.g., MIT, Apache 2.0, GPL) and include a link to the full license text.
- **Contributing Guidelines (optional)**
If you accept contributions, outline the process and any coding standards or review policies.
- **Acknowledgements**
Credit any funding sources, collaborators, or external libraries used.

A complete README contributes significantly to your research's findability, accessibility, reproducibility, and therefore it's impact. We encourage sharing your README file alongside your code in a public repository.

6. ENSURE REPRODUCIBILITY AND USABILITY

Publishing your code open source is crucial for reproducible research. Once again, [Guide for Reproducible Research](#) chapter from The Turing Way is a great start. You can also utilize the [Code-Auditor](#) developed by TDCC NES to review your code's quality and compliance with best practices.

7. ARCHIVE AND OBTAIN A DOI FOR YOUR RESEARCH SOFTWARE

If the main outcome of your research is the software code, you can investigate to publish it directly in a research software journal, such as [JORS](#). These journals often ask you to submit your code in a public repository, and the peer-review procedure also takes place as issues within the repository. This helps you to make improvements in pull requests, testing, and deployment cycle to have the whole development workflow in the same environment.

For most other scenarios, where you have data, software, and articles as your research output, you may publish and archive your source code in the [4TU.ResearchData](#) directly from your GitHub repository, providing it with one of the pre-approved licenses listed in this guideline. This will ensure that a particular release and version of your software is identified referenced by a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for that specific release. Please follow their guideline here: <https://data.4tu.nl/info/about-your-data/getting-started>

You can also utilize the Zenodo-GitHub [integration](#) to obtain a DOI for your GitHub repository via [Zenodo](#). Zenodo archives your repository and assigns a DOI to each new release you create, making your code citable. You can either manually upload your repository to Zenodo or link it to your GitHub account and automate the DOI generation with each release.

Here's a step-by-step guide:

1. Log in or sign up for a Zenodo account
2. Link your GitHub account to Zenodo:
 - Go to your Zenodo profile settings and select GitHub.
 - Enter your GitHub credentials.
3. Select the repository to archive:
 - Choose the GitHub repository you want to associate with Zenodo.
 - In Zenodo, you'll see a list of your GitHub repositories. Enable the one you want to archive.
4. Create a release on GitHub:
 - In your GitHub repository, create a new release.
 - Give it a title, description, and tag (e.g., v1.0.0).
5. Wait for Zenodo to synchronize:

- Zenodo will automatically archive your repository and assign a DOI to the release.
- It may take some time for the synchronization to complete.

6. Find the DOI in Zenodo:

- Return to Zenodo and check your repositories.
- You'll see your repository listed under "Enabled Repositories".
- The DOI will be displayed next to the repository.

7. Add the DOI badge (optional):

- You can add a DOI badge to your GitHub repository's README file.
- Zenodo provides the badge code in Markdown format.
- Copy and paste the code into your README.

You can also manually upload your research software repository to Zenodo:

- Go to "new upload" in Zenodo
- Add the necessary details about your project
- Click "reserve" to get the DOI

8. CITE TO YOUR OPEN-SOURCE CODE IN YOUR ARTICLE

As part of good research practice and in alignment with the FAIR4RS principles, it is essential to include a citation file (e.g., CITATION.cff) in the repository of your research software. Including a citation file enables other researchers to properly cite your code, which is important for:

- Tracking reuse of your software
- Receiving credit and recognition for your contributions
- Demonstrating the impact of your research software in academic and scientific communities

To support proper citation and long-term accessibility, it is strongly recommended that you:

- Assign a DOI to your code repository (via Zenodo, 4TU.ResearchData or DANS), which are integrated with GitHub
- Or provide the DOI of the publication that describes the software, if applicable.

If your software reuses code developed by others, you are ethically and academically obliged to cite those references in your work. Best practices for citing third-party research software include Listing the authors' names, affiliations, project or software name, and the DOI of the referenced code; Including this information in your repository's README.md or a dedicated section of your documentation.

To streamline citation management, we encourage you to generate a CITATION.cff file; a human- and machine-readable file that defines how your software should be cited. The [Citation File Format generator](#) is an easy-to-use tool that walks you through the process of creating this file.

Benefits of using a CITATION.cff file include:

- Interoperability with multiple platforms, including GitHub, Zenodo, and citation managers like Zotero
- Improved visibility and discoverability of your software

- Reduced manual work to cite your code

By facilitating proper citation, you make your software more findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, thereby supporting both open science and your own research impact.

9. REGISTER YOUR RESEARCH SOFTWARE TO YOUR UT PROFILE IN PURE

UT staff must register their research software on Pure Research Information System (RIS), and all data, software, and related materials underlying your research should be preserved for at least 10 years after the conclusion of the research.

Registering your software on Pure has multiple benefits.

As Dutch and EU taxpayers, the general society has a right to be informed of what we do with their contributions. We can use these lists to report to the government, open science communities, open-source groups, and the general society.

In the foreseeable future, sharing your research software open-source may be used as a metric to determine your scientific contributions among your other research output and merit alongside peer-reviewed publications, data, and teaching skills.

Companies collaborating with UT on software development demand that we keep track of the types of open-source licenses applied to different programs to prevent contamination.

10. PROMOTE AND MAINTAIN

You may consider promoting your open-source code on social media platforms to reach as many potential users as possible. You may benefit from online communities to obtain feedback, increase citations, receive help in maintaining and developing your code.

Some good practices in this field are:

- Keep your code and repository available at the UT and other relevant communities
- Share it on networks and respond to issues and questions
- Update README with changes

APPENDIX: UT PRE-APPROVED LICENSES

There are several types of open-source licenses made available to UT for application without further approval or permission beyond the requirements embedded in this guideline. They are listed below:

- [MIT](#)
- [BSD 3-clause](#)
- [Apache 2.0](#)
- [GPL 3.0](#)
- [EUPL 1.2](#)
- [Mozilla Public Licence](#)

To have your software licensed with one of these types, you need to follow the link and incorporate the whole text of the license. Within the license text, you also need to incorporate the following line, filling in the year and the names of the authors and/or contributors:

"Copyright (c) [Year] [Authors] University of Twente"